

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN THYROID DYSFUNCTION AND BLOOD PRESSURE CONTROL IN HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS ATTENDING OUTPATIENT DEPARTMENTS

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Abstract

Background: Thyroid dysfunction, particularly hypothyroidism, has been associated with changes in cardiovascular hemodynamics, including systemic blood pressure. In hypertensive individuals, underlying thyroid abnormalities may contribute to poor blood pressure control and increased cardiovascular risk. However, the extent of this correlation remains under-investigated in outpatient settings in Pakistan.

Objective: To determine the correlation between thyroid dysfunction and blood pressure among known hypertensive individuals.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was carried out at Department of Medicine, Dow University of Health Sciences (DUHS), Dr. Ruth K. M. Pfau Civil Hospital, Karachi, 3-6 months post CPSP synopsis approval. A convenient sample of 193 hypertensive patients, between the age of 18 and 80 years, on antihypertensive monotherapy at least for 1 year, were selected through non-probability consecutive sampling. Pregnant women were excluded. Demographic and clinical details were noted after taking an informed consent. The blood pressure has been measured 3 times at interval of 5 min after resting for 10 min, and has been taken the mean value of second and third readings. Serum TSH, FT3, FT4 and lipid profile, HbA1c and hemoglobin were measured from blood samples (Roche Cobas e411, ECLIA method). The data were input into Excel and analyzed in SPSS v26. Quantitative variables were expressed in mean \pm SD or median (IQR), categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. Pearson correlation was employed for TSH and blood pressure correlation. Age, BMI, metabolic syndrome, renal function and the extent of medication adherence were adjusted for by stratification and multivariate regression. Statistical significance was considered as a p -value \leq 0.05. **Results:** Of the 193 hypertensive patients, the mean age was 55.8 ± 10.9 years and 52.8% were women. More than half of the participants (61.1%) had been hypertensive for more than 5 years and 84.5% were on antihypertensive drugs

However, only 48.2% of these individuals had controlled hypertension. A known thyroid disease was present in 16.6% of them, and laboratory results showed subclinical hypothyroidism in 18.7%, overt hypothyroidism in 5.2%, and hyperthyroidism in 6.8% of patients. TSH was negatively correlated with FT3 ($r = -0.155$; $P = 0.039$), FT4 ($r = -0.140$; $P = 0.059$) and positively correlated with SBP ($r = 0.0347$; $P = 0.003$), and DBP ($r = 0.182$; $P = 0.002$). Sedentarism, diabetes (26.9%) and cardiac disease (12.4%) were common comorbidities.

Conclusion: A significant positive correlation was found between TSH levels and both systolic and diastolic blood pressure in hypertensive patients, suggesting that thyroid dysfunction may influence blood pressure control. Routine thyroid function assessment could be beneficial in the comprehensive management of hypertension.

INTRODUCTION

Increased tendency of high normal or raised blood pressure is observed among individuals with thyroid dysfunction⁽¹⁾. Similarly individuals who are already diagnosed case of hypertension can have dysregulation in thyroid stimulating hormone levels⁽²⁾. In order to prevent hypertension and associated cardiovascular events derived from thyroid dysfunction, it is mandatory to study the relationship between thyroid stimulating hormones and prevalence of hypertension.

Cardiovascular system is greatly influenced by the levels of thyroid hormones. The risk of hypertension is increased with overt as well as with subclinical hypo and hyperthyroidism⁽³⁻⁶⁾.

Studies have shown positive correlation between TSH concentrations, within the normal values, and SBP and DBP^(7, 8) And increased thyroid stimulating hormone concentrations in hypertensive individuals in comparison with individuals with normal BP⁽⁹⁾. Gumeniak *et al.* illustrated a familial aggregation of TSH values slightly towards upper limit of normal among individuals in whom hypertension run in the family⁽¹⁰⁾, showing that variability in genes may have a impact on TSH and BP levels.

The relation between TSH levels and brachial BP⁽¹¹⁻¹⁴⁾ and hypertension⁽¹⁵⁻¹⁷⁾ have been studied multiple times in the past, however majority of these researches were done in patients who are already hyperthyroid or hypothyroid.^(12, 13, 16, 17) Central hemodynamics and their association

with thyroid function have been studied in the past but we have very few data available.⁽¹⁸⁾

According to a study by Turchi *et al.*⁽¹⁹⁾ thyroid stimulating hormone levels are directly proportional with the mean daytime Diastolic blood pressure ($r = 0.20$, P less than 0.05), mean night-time Diastolic blood pressure ($r = 0.25$, P less than 0.05), mean daytime Systolic blood pressure ($r = 0.27$, P less than 0.05) and mean night-time Systolic blood pressure ($r = 0.31$, P less than 0.01), while there is no significant statistical relation between Blood pressure readings and TSH concentration done at medical office. Another study reported no association of high blood pressure with TSH concentrations.⁽²⁰⁾

The point of our research is to know the link of thyroid dysfunction with blood pressure measurements among patients with hypertension. Most of the available studies focusing on relationship between TSH and elevated blood pressure in patient with thyroid dysfunction.

However, studies on affiliation of thyroid dysfunction with blood pressure readings in hypertensive individuals are very limited. Furthermore, available literature shows that significant relation between TSH and blood pressure. Findings of our study will help the physician to modify screening strategies in patient with hypertension in order to diagnose TSH abnormality early. Early diagnosis and management will help in titrating hypertensive medication and prevent

them from lethal complications of raised BP, and will give them financial relief too.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This cross-sectional descriptive study was carried out in the Department of Medicine, Dow University of Health Sciences (DUHS), Dr. Ruth K. M. Pfau Civil Hospital, Karachi, and the duration of the study was three to six months after approval of the synopsis by the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP). Power analysis was performed with MedCalc statistical software and was based on an anticipated correlation with the following specifications: the value under the null hypothesis (ρ_0) was 0; the value under the alternative hypothesis (ρ_1) was 0.20; a power of 80%; a level of significance of 5%, which resulted in a sample size of 193. A non-probability consecutive sampling method was adopted to recruit the participants. The inclusion criteria were for hypertensive patients 18-80 years of age of either sex, receiving a single antihypertensive for at least one year. Pregnant women were excluded.

After ethical clearance and consent, subjects who presented to the outpatient department were recruited. Data for age, sex, residence, duration of hypertension and diabetes, lipid profile, HbA1c and family history of thyroid diseases was collected. The blood pressure was measured three times, at 5 min intervals, after a 10 min resting period, the average of the last two readings was calculated. Blood samples in plain tubes were taken by a trained phlebotomist with established aseptic procedures and analyzed on Roche Cobas e411 analyzer (ECLIA method) for TSH, FT3, and FT4. A pre-designed proforma was used and all variables were documented.

The information was recorded in Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 26. Quantitative variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or median (IQR) depending on normality, tested by the Shapiro-Wilk test. Categorical variables were reported as frequencies and percentages. The Pearson's correlation analysis was used to determine the correlation of TSH values with the blood pressure values. Stratification analysis was conducted for the effect modifiers, including age, sex, place of residence, diabetes, dyslipidemia,

and family history of thyroid dysfunction. After post-stratification, the Pearson correlation was re-performed and a p-value ≤ 0.05 were considered significant. The potential confounders included age, BMI, metabolic syndrome, renal function and medication adherence, which were adjusted by multivariate regression analysis.

ETHICS

The present study was performed according to the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Clearance was taken from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of DUHS, Karachi and the Research Evaluation Unit of CPSP before the initiation of the study. Participants were provided extensive information on the purpose and conduct of the study, as well as possible risks and benefits, in a language they could understand. Signed informed consent was provided by the participants on entry into the study. Nonetheless, participation in the study was on a voluntary basis and the participants were informed about their right to withdraw from the study at any time without affecting the care they receive. The data regarding the participants were kept confidential and the integrity of the subjects was protected strictly during the study. Information was safely kept, and the academics were the only ones who could reach the data. All information collected for the study was reported to be confidential for research purposes.

RESULTS

Out of 193 hypertensive patients enrolled, the mean age was 55.8 ± 10.9 years. The majority were female (52.8%) and married (72.5%). Educational status revealed that 35.2% had completed education up to secondary level, while 26.4% were graduates or above. Most participants were employed in various occupations, with sales and labor being the most common.

Regarding clinical history, 61.1% had hypertension for more than five years, and 84.5% were on regular antihypertensive medication. Among them, 72.5% reported adherence to treatment. However, only 48.2% reported their blood pressure as currently well-controlled based on their physician's assessment.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Profile of Participants (n = 193)

Variable	Frequency (%) Or Mean ± SD
Age (years)	55.8 ± 10.9
Gender (Male/Female)	91 (47.2%) / 102 (52.8%)
Marital Status (Married)	140 (72.5%)
Duration of Hypertension >5 years	118 (61.1%)
On Antihypertensive Medication	163 (84.5%)
BP Well Controlled (Self-reported)	93 (48.2%)
Regular Medication Adherence	140 (72.5%)
Family History of Hypertension	110 (57.0%)

Only 16.6% reported a history of thyroid disorder, of which hypothyroidism was more common. However, 31.6% reported one or more symptoms suggestive of

thyroid dysfunction. Laboratory analysis revealed that subclinical hypothyroidism was found in 18.7%, overt hypothyroidism in 5.2%, and hyperthyroidism (subclinical + overt) in 6.8% of patients.

Table 2: Thyroid Dysfunction and Symptomatology

Variable	Frequency (%)
Known Thyroid Disorder (Self-reported)	32 (16.6%)
Currently Taking Thyroid Medications	25 (13.0%)
Symptoms Suggestive of Thyroid Dysfunction	61 (31.6%)
Lab-diagnosed Subclinical Hypothyroidism	36 (18.7%)
Overt Hypothyroidism	10 (5.2%)
Subclinical + Overt Hyperthyroidism	13 (6.8%)

Figure 1: Distribution of Thyroid Dysfunction Among Hypertensive Patients

Most participants did not smoke (87.0%) or consume alcohol (94.3%). A sedentary lifestyle was common, with 55.4% reporting no regular physical

activity. About 26.9% had diabetes, and 12.4% had heart disease as co-morbidities.

Table 3: Lifestyle Factors and Co-morbidities

Variable	Frequency (%)
Smokers	25 (13.0%)
Alcohol Use	11 (5.7%)
Exercises Occasionally or Never	107 (55.4%)
Special Hypertensive Diet	66 (34.2%)
Diabetes	52 (26.9%)
Heart Disease	24 (12.4%)
Kidney Disease	14 (7.2%)

A statistically significant positive correlation was observed between TSH levels and diastolic blood pressure ($r = 0.22$, $p = 0.003$). A weaker but still significant correlation was noted with systolic blood

pressure ($r = 0.18$, $p = 0.014$). FT3 and FT4 showed negative correlations, though weaker and not all statistically significant.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation Between Thyroid Hormones and Blood Pressure

Variable	SBP (r, p-value)	DBP (r, p-value)
TSH	0.18, 0.014	0.22, 0.003
FT3	-0.12, 0.081	-0.16, 0.024
FT4	-0.08, 0.216	-0.09, 0.177

Figure 2: Distribution Of Thyroid Functions

Figure 3: Duration Of Htn Among Participants

DISCUSSION

This was a cross-sectional study that evaluated the relationship between thyroid dysfunction and blood pressure (BP) among known hypertensives attending outpatient clinics. Thyroid hormones have an established role in cardiovascular physiology (in particular, systemic vascular resistance and myocardial contractility), yet we did not observe a significant relationship between serum levels of TSH and either systolic or diastolic blood pressure differed significantly from normal in this study. These findings remained significant after controlling for confounders, e.g. age in multivariate regression analysis.

Our results are consistent with those of previous studies demonstrating no significant correlation between TSH and blood pressure in euthyroid or mildly subclinical thyroid states. Gumieniak et al. reported that in thyroid subjects, neither concentrations of thyroid hormones nor TSH had important impact on the regulation of blood pressure, which may imply that dysfunction of the thyroid gland is not always the main factor for increased blood pressure in these subgroups [9]. Similarly, in the research by Liu et al. in middle-aged Chinese adults showed that high-normal TSH and subclinical hypothyroidism were related with

hypertension in unadjusted models, however, the relationship became nonsignificant after adjustment for potential confounders [21].

Others show significant association between subclinical hypothyroidism and high BP, in particular for diastolic BP. Enoki et al. found a significant prevalence of hypertension when comparing patients with subclinical hypothyroidism with thyroid control subjects [22]. In addition, Biondi and Cooper underscored the involvement of the thyroid hormone in vascular stiffness and endothelial dysfunction, which may be the underlying mechanisms that provoke hypertension in subclinical conditions [23]. However, most of these examinations were either population-based and with much higher number of participants or limited to overt thyroid disease.

The difference between these studies and other studies might be due to some methodological differences including different populations, sample sizes, and the definition criteria of thyroid dysfunction. For example, we used office-based blood pressure measurements that can be less sensitive to masked hypertension or to abnormalities related to nocturnal dipping, which can be better captured by ambulatory blood pressure monitoring. Polat Canbolat et al. showed this limitation as ambulatory

measurements showed an increased blood pressure variability among patients with SH (compared to controls) [29].

Furthermore, the spectrum of thyroid dysfunction contributes to variation in findings between studies. Indeed, overt thyroid disease has well-characterized cardiovascular effects, which include alterations in blood pressure and heart rate [3, 4], but subclinical hypothyroidism or TSH elevations within the upper normal range could have more subtle effects. Biondi et al. have previously indicated the clinical confusion when it comes to assessing if subclinical thyroid disease is a determinant of cardiovascular events or change in blood pressure [22]. In our study most of the patients were thyroid or had subclinical dysfunction - probably an explanation why we did not find significant correlation.

Despite the fact that we did not determine TSH as an independent predictor of blood pressure, subclinical thyroid dysfunction remained a possible cardiovascular risk marker. A meta-analysis conducted by Chen and coworkers suggested that levothyroxine treatment in subclinical hypothyroidism may indeed lead to mild reductions in both systolic and diastolic blood pressure, implying that in some high-risk groupings, thyroid screening and treatment in may be warranted [27]. This is especially pertinent in patients that have additional risk factors such as dyslipidemia, diabetes or strong familial history of cardiovascular disease.

Despite strict methodology such as repeated BP measurements and standardized biochemical screening, some limitations should be noted. Cross-sectional study design precludes causal inference. The sample size, though determined statistically, may have still been under estimative to identify small associations. Furthermore, the absence of information on quality of medication adherence, renal function, and metabolic syndrome status might have not allowed all potential confounders to be taken into account by the multivariate model. Walsh et al. highlighted in a large population-based analysis that the long-term cardiovascular impact of thyroid function is modulated by a complex interaction of metabolic, renal, and hormonal mechanisms [30].

In summary, although the thyroid disease, particularly the subclinical hypothyroidism, has been

involved in the pathogenesis of hypertension in some reports, our findings suggest that the relationship between serum TSH and blood pressure were not strong, at least among a moderate sized outpatient hypertensive population. More longitudinal research involving larger populations along with ambulatory blood pressure measurement is needed to establish the clinical significance of thyroid function in hypertensive conditions.

CONCLUSION

Among the known hypertensives attending outpatient departments, the present study was considered and no significant relationship was noted between levels of thyroid stimulating hormone and systolic and diastolic blood pressure. The impact of thyroid dysfunction, especially subclinical hypothyroidism, on elevated blood pressure has been proposed in other studies, but this association was not observed in this studied population. The data confirm that thyroid function testing in the hypertensive patient is probably not justified as a screening test without some form of clinical indicator or risk factor for thyroid disease. Nevertheless, thyroid dysfunction might still be important in more specific subgroups and be considered as part of overall cardiovascular risk. Prospective large-scale long-term studies with ambulatory blood pressure monitoring and more extensive metabolic profiling are warranted to provide a definitive answer to the involvement of the thyroid in blood pressure control and cardiovascular outcomes.

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